

Table 1. Yield (t/ha) of Sita and Rimke in some provinces of Cambodia, 1989 and 1990.

Province (Location)	Sita	Rimke	Check
Phnom Penh (Chumcar Daung)	2.7	3.7	4.3
Kampong Speu (Chhbar Morn)	1.1	0.9	1.0
Kampong Speu (Phking)	1.0	0.8	0.8
Kandal (Udong)	1.1	1.3	1.6

Table 2. Morphoagronomic characteristics of Sita and Rimke compared with check variety C22.

Characteristic	Sita	Rimke	C22
Plant height (cm)	91	93	113
Duration (d)	91	103	135
Culm diameter (mm)	4.4	4.2	4.5
Root diameter (mm)	1.37	1.35	1.29
Panicle length (cm)	23.0	22.8	22.9
Tillers/plant (no.)	8	8	11
Leaf length (cm)	40.3	39.9	29.2
Leaf width (cm)	1.2	1.2	0.9
Flag leaf area (cm ²)	32.8	32.2	16.9
Panicle weight (g)	2.89	3.29	2.30
100-grain wt (g)	3.25	3.96	2.42
Grain length (mm)	7.0	7.0	6.00
Grain width (mm)	2.3	2.3	2.5
Grain type ^a	LS	LS	LB
Harvest index	0.51	0.49	0.43

^aS = long slender; LB = long bold.

derived from cross IRAT 13/Dourado Precoce//TOX490-1. ITA150 and ITA257 have been released as varieties in Africa and were introduced to Cambodia from the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Nigeria. Morphological characteristics of these varieties are in Table 2.

More than 100 Cambodians participating in a cooking quality test rated the grain quality characteristics of Sita and Rimke to be superior to that of IR64, IR72, Kru, and IR66.

ITA150 and ITA257 were released for cultivation by Cambodian farmers as Rimke and Sita, respectively. Both varieties are early maturing, have drought tolerance and blast resistance, and possess excellent grain quality. The varieties are spreading among farmers although no organized seed multiplication and extension systems exist. ■

Vandana (RR167-982), a new upland variety in the plateau region of Bihar, India

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About 5.1 million of India's 6.5 million ha of upland rice is concentrated in eastern India. Many upland farmers grow gora rice varieties, which have average yields of less than 1 t/ha.

RR167-982, derived from the cross C22/Kalakeri, was released as Vandana in 1992 by the Bihar State Variety Release Committee. It is for cultivation in the uplands of Chhotanagpur Plateau, which make up 33% of Bihar's upland area.

Vandana is semitall (115-130 cm) and has very good early and late vigor that allows proper stand establishment and competition with weeds (Table 1). It has a growth duration of 90-95 d and long roots (100 cm). Vandana's panicles are compact and exert fully; 1,000-grain weight is 24.2 g. Vandana has white kernels that are long and bold and of

Table 1. Characteristic features of Vandana and popular local variety Brown gora.

Character	Vandana	Brown gora
Plant height (cm)	115-130	110.9
Duration (d)	90-95	85-90
Vigor		
Early	Very good	Excellent
Late	Excellent	Excellent
Tillering (no.)	3.03	3.77
Panicle length (cm)	20.12	18.87
Panicle weight (g)	2.50	1.49
Lodging	Moderate	High
Drought reaction	Moderately resistant	Resistant
Spikelets/panicle (no.)	76	41
1,000-grain wt (g)	24.2	28.5
Grain yield (t/ha)	2.5-3.5	1.0-2.0
Grain color	Straw	Brown
Kernel color	White	Red
Kernel length (mm)	6.0	5.6
Kernel breadth (mm)	2.3	2.7
L-B ratio	2.53	2.07
Grain type	Long, bold	Short bold
Abdominal white	Present occasionally	Present
Water uptake (ml)	285	320
Cooked kernel length (mm)	9.8	9.6
Amylose content (%)	19.1	22.0
Isozyme group ^a	0	1

^aUsing Glaszmann's 1-6 scale.

Table 2. Yield data from multilocation evaluation of RR167-982 (Vandana) compared with local and improved checks. Bihar and Orissa, India, 1988-91.

Site	Vandana	Kalinga III	Birsadhan 101	Brown gora (local check)
<i>Hazaribag district, Bihar</i>				
Vigyan Kendra, Pondicherry	4.2	1.5	0.7	1.6
CRURRS	2.4	1.5	1.1	1.8
Barkatta	3.4	1.8	-	-
Handlo	2.3	1.5	-	1.2
Mean	3.2	1.6	0.9	1.5
<i>Giridih district, Bihar</i>				
Location 1	2.6	2.6	2.1	-
Location 2	1.9	1.9	1.2	1.1
Location 3	3.2	3.0	2.8	-
Location 4	4.7	3.6	4.2	-
Location 5	4.3	3.0	3.0	-
Mean	4.2	3.5	3.3	1.1
<i>Kalahandi district, Orissa</i>				
Location 1	2.9	2.6	2.7	2.5
Location 2	3.4	3.3	3.2	1.6
Mean	3.2	3.0	3.0	2.1

acceptable cooking and eating quality. It is moderately resistant to blast (BI) in uniform BI nurseries and to brown spot under field conditions. It is also resistant to sheath rot.

Vandana was evaluated under direct-seeded conditions in a station trial, multilocal testing, and in farmers' fields (Table 2) during 1988-91. It outyielded Brown gora, Birsadhan 101, and Kalinga III in grain and straw production. It averages 2.5-3.5 t/ha under normal conditions, although up to 4.7 t/ha have been recorded in farmers' fields. Vandana has also performed equally well in the highly drought-prone Kalahandi district of Orissa. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—deepwater

Performance of some promising deepwater rice (DWR) cultivars in northwestern Nigeria

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Seven lines of *Oryza sativa* and three lines of *O. glaberrima* were tested for flood tolerance and yield performance under rainfed deepwater condition at NCRI, Birnin Kebbi. Lines were evaluated against check FARO 14, which is a long-duration (170-198 d), photoperiod-sensitive variety.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. The gross plot was 4 × 3 m, and the net plot, 3.2 × 2.2 m. Two seeds per hill were sown on 17 Jun 1991 at a spacing of 20 × 20 cm.

A basal application of 30 kg NPK/ha was made at planting. Three weeks after seedling emergence, another 30 kg N/ha as urea was placed deeply among four hills before the floodwaters started in mid-July. Flood depth was recorded weekly from 16 Jul to 19 Nov. The maximum depth measured was 1.4 m on

Growth attributes and grain yield of deepwater rice cultivars.^a NCRI, Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria, 1989-91.

Cultivar	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)			Floodwater depth on weekly basis	
				1989	1990	1991	Date (1991)	cm
<i>O. glaberrima</i> ^b								
Jan-iri	99	161	389	2.2	3.0	2.4	16 Jul	7
Farin-iri	107	186	385	4.1	3.5	3.6	23 Jul	13
Yar-kaushe	101	181	388	3.0	3.3	3.3	30 Jul	18
<i>O. sativa</i>								
DM17	120	213	338	5.3	5.0	5.4	6 Aug	25
DA29	109	198	371	5.6	5.0	3.7	13 Aug	30
Maiada	109	201	361	5.4	5.5	5.4	20 Aug	47
BKN6986-17	113	190	316	4.3	5.6	2.7	27 Aug	53
FARO 4 (KAV-12)	119	200	416	2.4	3.2	3.4	3 Sep	68
							10 Sep	83
							17 Sep	100
FARO 6 (ICB)	115	220	358	3.6	2.4	4.9	24 Sep	121
FARO 7 (Mallong)	129	209	379	3.5	4.7	5.1	30 Sep	133
							10 Oct	140
FARO 14 (FRRS-43-111-2)	141	233	351	3.0	4.1	6.0	17 Oct	125
CV (%)		4.7	10.9			20.1	22 Oct	89
LSD (0.01)		18.1	ns ^c			1.63	29 Oct	75
							5 Nov	60
							12 Nov	54
							19 Nov	43

^aResults reported are 1991 data unless otherwise noted. ^bIndigenous types of rice. ^cns = not significant.